

Prediction of the torsional capacity of CFDST steel columns using extreme gradient boosting tree-based machine learning technique

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ABSTRACT

This study presents an eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) algorithm for predicting the torsional capacity of circular Concrete-Filled Double Skin Tubular (CFDST) steel columns under pure torsion. Utilizing a dataset of 806 columns generated through non-linear finite element analysis, the of XGBoost model outperforms existing empirical models with R^2 values of 99.5% (training) and 97.6% (testing). SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) framework aided in interpreting predictions at both global and local levels. Key influencing variables include concrete compressive strength, outer steel tube yield strength, outer steel tube thickness, and inner steel tube thickness. The study highlights the effectiveness XGBoost as a promising alternative to traditional empirical models for accurate torsional capacity predictions in CFDST steel columns.

Keywords: CFDST; Pure Torsion; tree-based ML technique; Feature Importance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent years have seen a growing interest in the use of concrete-filled double skin tubular (CFDST) steel columns as a compelling alternative to conventional reinforced concrete and structural steel columns, especially in high-rise building [1], and in bridge piers [2]. However, existing design codes provide no guidance for CFDST steel columns, even under the limit state of torsion.

This surge in interest has prompted numerous studies focusing on the performance of CFDST steel columns, particularly under pure torsion [3][4][5][6]. While these studies have contributed valuable insights, they have highlighted the pressing need for more precise predictive methods.

To address this challenge, this work explores the potential of Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), an advanced tree-based machine-learning algorithm, to improve the prediction of the torque capacity of CFDST steel columns. Machine-learning algorithms, including XGBoost, have widely been used for solving civil engineering problems and modeling the behaviour of various structural elements [7][8].

Furthermore, this work used the SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) framework to enhance the interpretability of model predictions. Beside the level of prediction, SHAP ensures that the results are also transparent and susceptible in engineering practice. Additionally, a comparative analysis between the XGBoost-based predictions and existing design codes is conducted to assess the robustness and reliability of the XGBoost approach in predicting the torsional capacity of CFDST steel columns.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 General workflow of the study

This study employs XGBoost model to predict the torque capacity of CFDST steel columns under pure torsion. XGBoost is a cutting-edge ML algorithm based on decision trees [7][8]. It excels in building predictive models by combining multiple smaller predictors, making it efficient and accurate. XGBoost employs a sequence of weak learners that work together to correct prediction errors from previous models. It can handle missing data, employs regularization to prevent overfitting, and delivers top-notch accuracy in both regression and classification tasks [9]. Hence, XGBoost is a powerful tool for modeling complex, nonlinear relationships in data. For detailed mathematical formulation of XGBoost, the reader is directed to e.g. [9][10]. The key steps encompassed within the methodology are illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Workflow of the study

(1) A dataset comprising 806 finite element analysis (FEA) CFDST specimens are collected and further information about the FEA are discussed in detail in Section 2.2 ; (2) The dataset is then split into 80% and 20% training and testing sets, respectively, using a random splitter, and then the XGBoost model is established on the training set and its performance evaluated on the testing set while improving its performance via hyperparameter tuning; (3) The model efficiency/accuracy is then evaluated by comparing its predictions with existing mechanical-based empirical models; and (4) SHAP is then implemented to have an insight into how the different features affect the prediction by the XGBoost model. For a detailed background of SHAP, the reader can be referred to e.g. [11][12].

2.2 Finite element analysis

2.2.1 Typical Experimental setup.

Fig. 2 depicts the cross-section of a CFDST columns, the typical experimental setup of a CFDST column under pure torsion (adapted from Huang *et al.* [4]), and the idealisation of the system into a mechanical model. Typically, using the hydraulic jack system, the horizontal force applied at a lever-arm distance produces a torque about the longitudinal axis of the CFDST column. To ensure that only pure torque is applied the CFDST column is typically tightly fixed at the top and bottom by an end-plate connection fixed by welding and bolted to the bottom and top steel platforms.

Fig. 2. Overview of the experimental protocol for a CFST specimen under pure torsion

2.2.2 NLFEA modelling description.

To assess the torque capacity of circular CFDST members under pure torsion, “solid” non-linear finite element analysis (NLFEA) model of CFDST columns is established using the ABAQUS program [13]. Within this NLFEA model, the outer and inner steel tubes, and the concrete annulus were discretised using 8-node brick elements with reduced integration (C3D8R). Since the concrete damage plasticity (CDP) model can effectively account for the compression and tension stiffening actions expected in members undergoing torque-induced shear stresses, the CDP model was utilised to simulate the damage plasticity behaviour of the sandwiched concrete. The CDP model was defined with the following parameters [14]: *Dilation angle* = 31° , *Eccentricity* = 0.1, $f_{b0}/f_{c0} = 1.16$, $K = 0.67$, and *viscosity parameter* = 0.003.

Fig. 3 illustrates the grid meshing of the CFDST components and boundary conditions adopted in the NLFEA model. To simulate interactions at the interface between the steel tubes and the sandwiched concrete, a solid contact and penalty friction formulation for normal and tangential behaviour was employed, respectively. It is worth noting that the friction coefficient for this NLFEA model was set at 0.6 [15].

Fig. 3. NLFEA model depicting grid meshing of the CFDST elements and boundary conditions.

Since plastic hardening behaviour is expected for steel tubes under torsional load, the following quadratic plastic flow model proposed by Esmaeily and Xiao [16] was adopted in the NLFEA steel tubes. Finally, the compression and tension behaviour of the sandwiched confined concrete were modelled using the models of Mander *et al.* [17], and Pagoulatou *et al.* [18], respectively.

2.2.3 NLFEA validation

Six (6) CFDST members with circular hollow sections on the inner and outer tubes were considered for validation of the NLFEA approach. These specimens were taken from an experimental protocol conducted by Huang *et al.* [4]. For a detailed description of the fabrication and experimental setup of these columns,

please refer to their work [4]. However, salient details of their geometric and material properties are given as shown in *Table 1* and comprehensive information about both the torsional capacity predicted by the NLFEA model ($T_{u,NLFEA}$) and the measured value ($T_{u,expt}$). To gauge the accuracy and validation of the NLFEA, the model error of the NLFEA, defined as $T_{u,expt} / T_{u,NLFEA}$ [19], [20] shows a mean value of 1.05 and a coefficient of variation of 0.08 (as outlined in *Table 1*). The developed NLFEA model is presently employed to create a database of 806 CFDST specimens for developing the XGBoost model.

Table 1. Material and geometric properties of CFDST specimens adopted from Huang *et al.* [4]

S/N	D_o , mm	t_o , mm	D_i , mm	t_i , mm	f_{yo} , MPa	f_{yi} , MPa	f_{cu} , MPa	$T_{u,expt}$ kNm	$T_{u,NLFEA}$, kNm	$T_{u,expt}/T_{u,NLFEA}$ [-]
CO1I1	165	3	42	3	260	326.6	50	24.6	25.52	0.96
CO1I2	165	3	75	5	260	355.4	50	33.2	34.16	0.97
CO2I1	165	4	42	3	286.4	326.6	50	32.3	31.64	1.02
CO2I2	165	4	75	5	286.4	355.4	50	42.1	40.28	1.05
CO3I1	165	4.6	42	3	355.4	326.4	50	48.8	42.5	1.15
CO3I2	165	4.6	75	5	365.6	355.4	50	54.3	47.83	1.14
Mean	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.05
CoV	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.08

NOTE:

D_o =outer steel tube diameter, t_o =outer steel tube thickness, D_i =inner steel tube diameter, t_i =inner steel tube thickness, f_{yo} =outer steel tube yield strength, f_{yi} = inner steel tube yield strength, f_{cu} = concrete cube compressive strength, $T_{u,expt}$ =torque-capacity predicted from experiment, $T_{u,NLFEA}$ =torque-capacity predicted from NLFEA

2.3 Database description

A dataset consisting of 806 CFDST members compiled using the NLFEA model established in the previous section was used here to build the XGBoost model. The database was generated such as to include even out-of-code parameters i.e. high strength steels and concretes. *Fig. 4* illustrate the frequency distribution of various input parameters as well as the output parameter within database, respectively. From linear regression, parameters t_o , D_o , D_i and f_{cu} seem to have a positive correlation with the torsional capacity T_u . However, other parameters such t_i , f_{yo} and f_{yi} seem to have insignificant impact on T_u . However, this analysis is based in linear assumptions but SHAP analysis via the XGBoost was used to reveal any non-linear relationships that may exist between each input parameters and the torque capacity.

2.4 Data preprocessing and model training

The raw dataset underwent pre-processing steps for ML model suitability. Numerical data underwent stratified random sampling (80% training, 20% testing). Feature scaling employed *StandardScaler* from Scikit-Learn [21]. No missing values were detected, maintaining the dataset size (806 entries). The target variable was separated from features to enhance model generalization. During training, XGBoost model performance was evaluated using metrics like coefficient of determination (R^2) and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), where higher R^2 and MAPE values indicated better performance [8].

2.5 Model tuning and cross-validation

The model's performance was improved through rigorous hyperparameter tuning and five-fold cross-validation using Grid Search [21]. The best XGBoost model in this study was built with hyperparameters set as follows: $n_estimators=150$, $learning_rate=0.1$, $min_child_weight=0.1$, $max_depth=3$, $random_state=20$, $reg_alpha =0.1$, and $reg_lambda=0.5$.

Fig. 4. Distribution of input parameters against the torsional capacity in the dataset of 806 CFDST columns

3 RESULTS

3.1 Performance of XGBoost

High R^2 values, both training (99.5%) and testing (97.6%) sets, demonstrate the model's impressive explanatory power, capturing over 95% of the variability in torque capacity data. The model's accuracy is further validated by low MAPE values, particularly in the training set, highlighting minimal average percentage error and exceptional predictive precision. The visual representation (Fig. 5) of predicted versus actual torque capacity values showcases a harmonious correlation, evident through gracefully intertwined blue and red datapoints across both training and testing sets. In conclusion, the XGBoost model proves highly effective in predicting CFDST torque capacity.

Fig. 5 Performance of the XGBoost model

3.2 Comparison with empirical models

The XGBoost model was compared to two empirical models proposed by previous researchers [3] [4]. The specific calculation formulas are described and given in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of currently available analytical formulas for predicting the torque-capacity of CFDST columns in pure torsion

Huang et al. [4]	Lu et al. [3]
$T_{uc2} = \gamma_t W_{sct} \tau_{scy} + W_{si} \tau_{yi}$	$T_u = T_{so} + T_c + T_{si}$
$T_u = T_{so} + T_c + T_{si}$	$T_{so} = 2A_{so,0} t_o \tau_{so}$
$\tau_{scy} = (0.422 + 0.313\alpha_n^{2.33})\xi^{0.134} f_{scy}$	$\tau_{so} = \frac{\sqrt{1-\alpha^2}}{\sqrt{3}} f_{yo}$
$f_{scy} = C_1 \chi^2 f_{yo} + C_2 (1.14 + 1.02\xi) f_{ck}$	$\alpha = -0.0928\chi - 0.0272/\xi_3 + 0.3356$
$\tau_{yi} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} f_{yi}$	$\chi = \frac{d}{D-2t_o}$
$\gamma_t = (-0.22\chi + 0.273) \ln(\xi) - 0.133\chi + 1.29$	$\xi_3 = \frac{f_c A_c}{f_{yo} A_{so} + f_{yi} A_{si}}$
$C_1 = \frac{\alpha}{1+\alpha}$	$T_{si} = 2A_{si,0} t_i \tau_{si}$
$C_2 = \frac{1+\alpha_n}{1+\alpha}$	$A_{si,0} = \frac{\pi(d-t_i)^2}{4}$
$\xi = \frac{\alpha_n f_{yo}}{f_{ck}}$	$\tau_{si} = \frac{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}{\sqrt{3}} f_{yi}$
$\alpha = \frac{A_{so}}{A_c}$	$\beta = -0.4982\chi + 0.0524\xi_3 + 0.4012$
$W_{sct} = \frac{\pi(D^4-d^4)}{16D}$	$T_c = W_p c \tau_c$
$W_{si} = \frac{\pi(d^4-(d-2t_{si})^4)}{16d}$	$W_p c = \frac{\pi((D-2t_o)^3-d^3)}{12}$
	$\tau_c = f_t \sqrt{1 + \frac{f_c}{f_t} \cdot \frac{\sigma_c}{f_c}} \left(1 - 0.8233 \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{f_c} \right)^{4.5} \right)$
	$f_c = 0.67 f_{cu}$
	$f_t = 0.395 f_{cu}^{0.55}$
	$\sigma_c / f_c = \frac{\alpha f_{yo} A_{so} + \beta f_{yi} A_{si}}{f_c A_c}$
	$A_c = \frac{\pi(D-2t_o)^2}{4} - \frac{\pi d^2}{4}$

NOTATIONS: W_{sct} - Polar section modulus of outer steel tube and concrete, W_{si} - Polar section modulus of inner steel tube, W_{so} - Polar section modulus of outer steel tube, α - Steel ratio, α_n - Nominal steel ratio, χ - CFDST hollow ratio, τ_{scy} - Strength of the composite section of outer steel tube and concrete under torsion, τ_y - Yield strength of steel in shear, τ_{yi} - Yield strength of inner steel tube in shear, τ_{yo} - Yield strength of outer steel tube in shear, ξ - Confinement factor A_c - Cross-sectional area of the sandwiched concrete, A_{ce} - Nominal core concrete cross-sectional area, A_{sco} - Cross-sectional area of the outer steel tube and the sandwiched concrete, A_{sc} - Cross-sectional area of CFDST member, A_{si} - Cross-sectional area of inner steel tube A_{sc} - Cross-sectional area of outer steel tube f_{ck} - Characteristic concrete compressive strength, f_{cu} - 28-day characteristic concrete cube compressive strength, f_c' - Cylinder concrete compressive strength

The XGBoost model outperforms the two empirical models in terms of predictive performance (see Fig. 6). The XGboost model has a mean error of 1.02, while the Huang *et al.* [4] model has a mean error of 2.46

and the Lu *et al.* [3] model has a mean error of 2.76. The XGBoost model also has a lower standard deviation than the other two models, which indicates that its predictions are more consistent. In addition to the mean and standard deviation of the errors, the figure also shows the distribution of the errors for each model. The distribution of the errors for the XGBoost model is more tightly clustered around the mean than the distributions of the errors for the other two models. This suggests that the XGBoost model would less likely to make large errors.

Fig. 6. Performance comparison between the empirical models and the XGBoost model.

3.3 SHAP interpretation of XGBoost model

3.3.1 Global SHAP analysis

Understanding what affects the torque capacity of CFDST columns is vital for designing them optimally. SHAP analysis is a powerful tool that helps reveal the importance of different features in the XGBoost model via both global and local levels. Global SHAP shows us the overall impact each feature has on torque predictions (see Fig. 7). The top-four ranked parameters are concrete compressive strength (f_{cu}), outer steel tube yield strength (f_{yo}), outer steel tube thickness (t_o), and inner steel tube thickness (t_i). It can be seen in Fig. Fig. 7 (b), that the blue dots represents lower feature values and the red dots high feature values indicating that nearly all parameters have a positive influence on the SHAP values indicating that increasing the values of these parameters increases the torque capacity of CFDST columns, in line with observations in [3] [4].

Fig. 7. Global SHAP summary plots

3.3.2 Local SHAP analysis: Interplay among input features and effect on torque capacity

Global SHAP only presents averages but fails to reveal certain critical features. This is where local SHAP comes in, providing a closer look at individual data points. Analysing the XGBoost model for CFDST torque capacity under pure torsion, local SHAP reveals key insights as shown in Fig. 8 concerning the interplay between input features. In all the plots in Fig. 8, there is evident interrelationship between the input features and their contribution to the overall prediction of the XGBoost model.

Fig. 8. Local SHAP dependency plot showing interaction among input features and the effect on torque capacity.

D_o against f_{cu} : Fig. 8(a) shows that for the CFDST member, a larger outer steel tube diameter D_o combined with a high concrete compressive strength f_{cu} has the positive effect on the prediction of the torque capacity using the XGBoost model. Conversely, CFDST columns with smaller D_o exhibit negative SHAP values for low, medium, or high f_{cu} but the negative SHAP values are marginally below zero indicating a minor influence on the reduction in torque capacity.

t_o against f_{yo} : Fig. 8(b) shows that for the outer steel tube of the CFDST member, a larger thickness t_o combined with a high yield strength f_{yo} has the positive effect on the prediction of the torque capacity using the XGBoost model but CFDST columns with smaller t_o exhibit high negative SHAP values for high values of f_{yo} indicating a large influence on the reduction in torque capacity.

D_i against f_{cu} : Fig. 8(c) shows that for CFDST member, a larger inner steel tube diameter D_i combined with a high concrete compressive strength f_{cu} has the positive effect on the prediction of the torque capacity using the XGBoost model. Conversely, CFDST columns with smaller and medium D_i exhibit negative SHAP values for low, medium, or high f_{cu} but the negative SHAP values are marginally below zero indicating a relative minor influence on the reduction in torque capacity.

t_i against f_{yo} : Fig. 8(d) shows that for the relationship between inner steel tube thickness t_i and strength of outer steel tube f_{yo} is not clear in the XGBoost model. This is expected since the two variables are intuitively expected to be independent.

f_{yo} against f_{cu} : Fig. 8(e) shows that for large values of f_{yo} and f_{cu} have a positive impact on the prediction of torque capacity by the XGBoost model. A linear relationship can be observed but for very small values of f_{yo} , the SHAP value is only negative for small values of f_{cu} but always positive for medium and high values

of f_{cu} . This indicates that regardless of the values that f_{yo} may take, f_{cu} has on average a positive impact on the prediction of the torque capacity using the present XGBoost model.

f_{yi} against D_i : Fig. 8(f) shows a somewhat exponential relationship between f_{yi} and D_i indicating that a combination of large values of these two parameters leads to a somewhat exponential increase in the prediction of the torque capacity via the XGBoost model. However, negative SHAP values are observed for a combination of smaller values of f_{yi} and high values of D_i , implying that f_{yi} has a slightly negative impact (i.e. SHAP values marginally less than zero) on the torque capacity when the hollow section ratio of the CFDST column increases.

4 DISCUSSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR ENGINEERING PRACTICE

The analysis of the XGBoost model's performance, empirical model comparisons, and SHAP analysis provides valuable insights for engineering practice in the design of CFDST columns under pure torsion. The superior predictive power of the XGBoost model, evident in high R^2 values and low mean errors, positions it as a reliable tool for engineers seeking accurate torque capacity predictions. Critical parameters such as concrete compressive strength, outer steel tube yield strength, outer steel tube thickness, and inner steel tube thickness, identified through global SHAP analysis, offer specific targets for optimisation [22]. The nuanced relationships revealed in the local SHAP analysis emphasise the interplay between these parameters, providing engineers with a detailed understanding for tailored design decisions. Practical implications include the prioritisation of key parameters [23] to enhance torque resistance and the incorporation of advanced machine learning techniques in structural engineering practices. This study marks bridges the gap between traditional empirical models and tree-based ML tools, empowering engineers to achieve more efficient and informed CFDST column designs for optimal structural performance [22].

5 CONCLUSIONS

The XGBoost model exhibits good predictive performance for CFDST steel columns' torque capacity under pure torsion. Outperforming existing empirical models, it showcases a mean error of 1.02 and a consistent distribution of model errors. Feature importance analysis through SHAP highlighted the significant impact of concrete compressive strength, outer steel tube yield strength, outer steel tube thickness, and inner steel tube thickness. Local SHAP analysis revealed the interplay of the input features and the effect on the predicted torque capacity by the XGBoost model. Local SHAP analysis via dependency plots revealed that the XGBoost model is not a black box model but can be used hybrid with mechanics-based models to understand the behaviour of CFDST columns under pure torsion. These insights do not only enhance the understanding of the system but also provide a basis for optimising CFDST column design. Future research could include among others, refinement, and expansion of torque capacity predictive models for CFDST columns.

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